

Molecular detection of extended spectrum β -lactamase in gram negative bacteria isolated from intensive care unit patients in Wasit province, Iraq

Rana Essa muslem ^{1,*}, Rana H Raheema ¹ and Qasim Dawood Yasir ²

¹ Department of Medical Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Wasit, Iraq.

² Department of Pediatric, Faculty of Medicine, University of Wasit, Iraq.

World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2022, 12(02), 094–104

Publication history: Received on 23 September 2022; revised on 12 November 2022; accepted on 15 November 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2022.12.2.0178>

Abstract

Intensive care units (ICU) are epicenters for the emergence of antibiotic-resistant Gram negative bacteria and multi-resistant Gram positive infections, largely due to the inappropriate use of antimicrobials. In this study, a total of 100 clinical specimens (urine, sputum and pus) were collected from patients admitted in the ICU. Results showed eighty two were positive growth culture. The findings of the disc diffusion method used to test the isolates for antibiotic susceptibility showed that Amikacin was the most effective antibiotic against *klebsiella pneumonia* and *pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Phenotypically survey of ESBLs for all isolates were ESBL producers, of these, 13(68.4%) isolates were determined as ESBLs-producers following confirmatory testing to be ESBLs producers. Whereas, genotypically no isolate had ESBLs producers CTX-M-type ESBL. The prevalence of TEM, SHV, and OXA-1 were as follow: *bla_{SHV}* 3(23 %). While *bla_{TEM}* and *bla_{OXA-1}* genes were absent among all isolates. Phenotypically survey of ESBLs, for (20) isolates *pseudomonas aeruginosa* 20(100%) isolates were ESBLs producers of these, 12(60%) isolates were determined as ESBLs-producers following confirmatory testing to be ESBLs producers. While genotypically isolates were ESBL producers 1(8.3%) of the isolates were ESBLs producers CTX-M-type ESBL was the most prevalent CTX-M2 was 1(8.3%) , CTX-M1 and CTX-M9 were absent among all isolates. The prevalence of TEM, SHV, and OXA-type1 were as follow: *bla_{SHV}* 4(33%). While *bla_{TEM}* and *bla_{OXA-1}* genes were absent among all isolates. Phenotypically survey of ESBLs, for (17) isolates *E. coli* 17(100%) isolates were ESBLs producers of these, 10(58.8%) isolates were determined as ESBLs-producers following confirmatory testing to be ESBLs producers. Whereas, Genotypically no isolate ESBLs producers CTX-M-type ESBL, prevalence of TEM, SHV, and OXA-1 were as follow: *bla_{SHV}* 1(10%), *bla_{OXA-1}* 1(10%) . While *bla_{TEM}* gene was absent among all isolates.

Keywords: Antibiotic susceptibility; ESBLs; Gram negative bacteria; Intensive care unit

1. Introduction

Intensive care units (ICUs) are important departments at the hospital for nosocomial infections. Although an ICU has 5%– 10% of the hospital beds, 25%–50% of the nosocomial infections originate from the ICU [1]. Both ventilator-related pneumonia (VRP) and catheter-related urinary tract infections (CRUIs) are the most common infections in the ICU [2]. Many risk factors are responsible for nosocomial infection in the ICU [3]. Some of the risk factors are related to the patient, whereas the others are related to the external factors. It is known that improving the risk factors decreases the infection, mortality, morbidity, and cost [2,4]. The environmental conditions affect the infection rate in the ICU [5]. Hospital-acquired infections (HAI) have been recognized for over a century as a critical problem affecting the quality of healthcare, and they constitute a major source of adverse healthcare outcomes [6]. The emergence of multidrug-resistant bacteria (MDRB) has become a public health problem, creating a new burden on medical care. In addition to

* Corresponding author: Rana Essa muslem

Department of Medical Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Wasit, Iraq.

this, ICU patients have an increased risk of infection due to their underlying diseases or conditions, impaired immunity, and exposure to multiple invasive devices (mechanical ventilation, central venous catheters (CVC), and urinary tract catheters), the incidence of ICU-HAI is 5–10-times higher than HAI rates in general wards [7]. Intensive care units (ICU) are epicenters for the emergence of antibiotic-resistant Gram negative bacteria and multi-resistant Gram positive infections, largely due to the inappropriate use of antimicrobials [8]. The aim was presented to detect spread of bacterial isolates from patients in ICU in Kut City, Wasit Province, Iraq, and to characterize it at the level of molecular analyses of its Phylogenic and antimicrobial resistance genes.

2. Material and Methods

A cross-sectional study was done in the intensive care unit (ICU) of the Alzahraa, Alkarama hospitals from the 3rd October 2021 to 20th February 2022. A total of 100 clinical samples, including: urine, sputum and pus culture media such as mannitol salt agar, MacConkey agar, blood agar, and chocolate agar. The growth showed different bacterial colonies whose morphological and biochemical characteristics were tested. Then DNA was extracted; purity and concentration were confirmed with Nanodrop. The purity of gram negative bacteria (1.8-2), and the concentration was between 50-360 ng/μl.

Table 1 Primers' sequence of gram-negative bacteria

MultiplexPCR pool	Primers	Sequences (5'-3')	Size(bp)	References
MultiplexI TEM, SHV and OXA -1 Like	Multi TSO-Tfor	CATTTCCGTGTGCGCCCTTATTC	800	(Dallenne <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	Multi TSO-Trev	CGTTCATCCATAGTTGCCTGAC		
	Multi TSO- S-for	AGCCGCTTGAGCAAATTA AAC	713	
	Multi TSO-Srev	ATCCCGCAGATAAAATCACCAC	564	
	Multi TSO-Ofor	GGCACCAGATTCAACTTTCAAG		
	Multi TSO-Orev	GACCCCAAGTTTCTGTAAAGTG		
Multiplex-II: CTX-M group 1, group 2 and group 9	Multi CTXMGP1 -for	TTA GGA ART GTG CCG CTG YAb		688
	Multi CTXM GP1-2-rev	CGATATCGTT GGT GGTRCCATb		
	Multi CTXMGP 2-for	CGTTAACGGC ACGATGAC	404	
	MultiCTX MGP1-2- rev	CGATATCGTT GGTGGTRCCATb		
	Multi-CTXMGP9-F	TCAAGCCTGCCGATCTGGT	561	
	Multi-CTXMGP9-R	TGATTCTCGCCGCTGAAG		

Production of ESBLs was initially phenotypically discovered using the disk diffusion method (screening test), and was then verified using the double disc synergy test (DDST) [9]. Whereas an isolate is considered to be ESBL producer in the case when it shows resistance to one or more of the 3rd. Generation cephalosporins as follows: cefotaxime (≤ 27mm); ceftazidime (≤ 22mm); ceftriaxone (≤ 25mm) and aztreonam (≤ 27mm).

Table 2 Thermal cycling program for multiplex pool.1 CTX group

Genes	PCR cycling profile	Products size
<i>bla_{ctx1,2,9}</i>		Ctx1 688 Ctx2 404 Ctx9 561

Table 3 Thermal cycling program for multiplex pool.2 TSO

Genes	PCR cycling profile	Products size
<i>bla</i> TEM, <i>SHV</i> ,and <i>OXA-1</i>		TEM 800 SHV 713 OXA-1 564

According to who adapted this protocol as a reliable and efficient tool for the identification via multiplex PCR assays of the most common encoding of the beta-lactamase genes for gram negative bacteria? Gel Electrophoresis and Documentation [10] and finally the data's statistical analysis has been carried out with the use of SAS (Statistical Analysis System - version 9.1) [11].

3. Results and discussion

The current study was conducted on a total of one hundred clinical specimens (urine, sputum and pus) were collected from patients admitted in the ICU. Eighty two were positive growth culture distributed according to the patient's age, the highest incidence was among 20-29 age groups with (25.6 %). While the lowest incidence was among (50-59) and (70-79) age group (3.6%),(3.6%) respectively ,the mean \pm SD of age was 15.556 ranging from 1 years to 90 years.

Eighty two pure positive culture, 30(36.5%) were female of patients 52(63.5%) were male and admitted to the intensive care unit distributed 69 (84.1%) gram-negative bacteria. while gram positive 13(15.8%) .As shown in Table (4).

Table 4 Bacteria distribution according to specimens

Culture result	Urine No(%)	Sputum No(%)	Pus No(%)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	3 (3%)	11 (11%)	5 (5%)
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	0 (0%)	1 (1%)	0 (0%)
<i>E. Coli</i>	11 (11%)	3 (3%)	6 (6%)
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	4 (4%)	9 (9%)	7 (7%)
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (5%)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	0 (0%)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	1 (1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
<i>Burkholderia cepacia group</i>	0 (0%)	1 (1%)	0 (0%)
<i>Pantoea spp</i>	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (1%)
<i>Staph.aureus</i>	2 (2%)	3 (3%)	6 (6%)
<i>Staph heamoltyius</i>	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)
Total	21	30	32

Bacterial isolates that were obtained from the clinical specimens have been initially characterized based on the cultural morphology as well as the biochemical tests. Results of culture showed colonies on MacConkey agar pink color with

precipitation of bile salt around colonies, the refers to *Escherichia coli* isolates while results of biochemical tests for *Escherichia coli* were had given positive test for catalase, indole, methyl red, but negative for oxidase, voges-proskauer, simmon citrate, and TSI test showed A/A with gas , without H₂S. This results diagnostic for *Escherichia coli* .Similar results was recorded by [12–14].

Results of identification of *klebsiella pneumoniae* were showed pink lactose fermenter mucoid colonies on MacConkey agar. Positive test for urease, voges-proskauer, simmon citrate , but negative for oxidase, methyl red, motility test, indole and TSI test showed A/A with gas , without H₂S . Further confirmation done using Vitek2. Similar results were recorded by [15, 16].

Results of *Acinetobacter baumannii* showed nonmotile and give negative result to oxidase, indole, methel red, voges proskauer and avirable to urea. All isolates were positive to catalase , simmons citrate and triple-sugur-iron test was alkaline / no change, these results are identical with those obtained by [17,18]. The results of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed that all isolates had given negative result for indole, methyl red, voges proskauer and urease test also, citrate assimilation was positive, motility was positive and TSI alkaline / alkaline or Alkaline / no change with no production of H₂S and gas and isolated from cetrimide agar colonies appeared mucoid, smooth in shape, fruity odour, fluorescent green, and creamy pigments these results agreed with what mentioned by [13,18–20].

The results of *Proteus mirabilis* appear as bacilli, rapidly motile by flagella. Swarming phenomena on blood agar plate. It is non-lactose fermenter so it gives a pale colony on macConky agar. Negative test for indole and voges-proskauer but positive test for urease, simmon s citrate , H₂S is produced ,nitrate reduction motility and methyl reed .Similar finding was recorded by [15,18].

The results of *Serratia. marcescens*, showed that isolate had given result for indole, urease test , citrate assimilation , motility and catalase positive . Methyl red, voges proskauer and oxidase negative and TSI alkaline / acidic or acidic / acidic with no production of H₂S and gas.The results of *Burkholderia cepacia* complex showed that isolate had given a result at negative for indole. But positive for methyl red, voges proskauer, urease test, citrate assimilation, motility, catalase and oxidase, TSI alkaline / acidic with no production of H₂S and gas.

The results of *Pantoea spp* showed that isolate had given result for indole methyl red, urease test, motility,and oxidase negative. Voges-proskauer citrate assimilation, catalase positive, TSI alkaline / acidic with no production of H₂S and gas. The results *Enerobacter cloacae* indicated that isolate had given result for indole, methyl red,urease test , motility and oxidase negative. Voges-proskauer, citrate assimilation and catalase was positive. TSI alkaline / acidic with no production of H₂S and gas. The results of *staphylococcus aureus* appeared that isolates had given result for indole was negative , methyl red was positive , voges-proskauer was positive , urease test was positive , citrate assimilation was positive, motility was negative and TSI acidic / acidic with no production of H₂S and gas , catalase was positive , coagulase was positive and oxidase was positive this results are consistent with findings from other Iraqi studies [20,21]. Also similar result was recorded by [21–23]. On blood agar *staphylococcus haemolyticus* fermenters as yellow colonies. Further biochemical tests were necessary for identification of *staphylococcus haemolyticus* from other species, all isolates were positive to catalase test, but negative for coagulase and oxidase [24]. The results of *Enterococcus faeciu* showed that isolate had given negative results for indole, urease test, citrate assimilation, motility, catalase and oxidase. But positive result for voges-proskauer. TSI acidic / acidic with no production of H₂S and gas.

3.1. Antibiotic susceptibility test of *klebsiella pneumonia* isolates

The maximum resistance level of study to Ampicillin was 100 % followed by Ceftriaxone , Azitreonam ,Cefotaxime , Ceftazidime , and Cefepime with (95%) respectively , (Cefixime and Piperacillin)(90%) respectively , (Ciprofloxacin 79%), (Trimethoprime and Amoxicillin_clavulanic acid) (74%) respectively , (Cefoxitin 69 %),(Meropenem ,Nalidixic acid ,and Piperacillin _tazobactam) (68%)respectively, (Gentamicin and Levofloxacin) (63%), (Imipenem 53%). As shown in figure (1).

The results revealed maximum resistant to Ampicillin was (100 %). These data are in agreement with the study performed by [25,26]. Resistance percentage of *klebsiella pneumoniae* to ciprofloxacin (79%) was agreement with the study performed by [27,28] and [16], Study revealed that amoxicillin -clavulanic acid (77%) by [16] agreed with this results. The maximal *klebsiella pneumoniae* sensitivity has been to (amikacin 58 %), and (nitrofurantoin 47 %), which in agreement with [16,29]. The medical literature uses the terms multidrug-resistant (MDR), extensively drug-resistant (XDR), and pandrug-resistant (PDR) bacteria to describe the various patterns of resistance seen in healthcare-associated, antimicrobial-resistant bacteria. It was divided according to the criteria by [30].The percentages were as follows MDR were (47%), XDR were (21.5%) and PDR were (31.5%).

CRO = Ceftriaxone, AZT= Aztreonam, CTX = Cefotaxime, CAZ = Ceftazidime, AUG=Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, IMI=Imipenem, MRB= Meropenem, NA= nalidixic acid, PRL=piperacillin, AMP = Ampicillin, F = Nitrofurantoin, FEP=Cefepime, CIP=Ciprofloxacin, FOX = Cefoxitin, TZP=piperacillin-tazobactam, CN = Gentamicin,CFM = Cefixime, TM=Trimethoprim, AK=Amikacin ,LEV=levofloxacin

Figure 1 The percentage of antibiotics susceptibility profiles of *K.pneumonia*

3.2. Antibiotic susceptibility test of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates

CRO = Ceftriaxone, AZT= Aztreonam, CTX = Cefotaxime, CAZ = Ceftazidime, AUG=Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, IMI=Imipenem, MRB= Meropenem, NA= nalidixic acid, PRL=piperacillin, AMP = Ampicillin, F = Nitrofurantoin, FEP=Cefepime, CIP=Ciprofloxacin, FOX = Cefoxitin, TZP=piperacillin-tazobactam, CN = Gentamicin,CFM = Cefixime, TM=Trimethoprim, AK=Amikacin ,LEV=levofloxacin

Figure 2 The percentage of antibiotics susceptibility profiles of *P. aeruginosa*

The maximum resistance level of study for (Azitreonam ,Ceftriaxone ,Cefotaxime ,and Ceftazidime) (100 %)respectively followed by (Cefepime, Piperacillin ,and (Ampicillin) (80%)respectively followed by (Meropenem , Nalidixic acid , Ciprofloxacin and Amoxicillin - clavulanic acid and Cefixime) (60%)respectively . As shown in figure (2).

These results agree with study in Wasit [31,32] which found to be highly resistant to (ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, azitreonam and cefotaxime) (100%) respectively. The maximal *pseudomonas aeruginosa* sensitivity has been to (amikacin, trimethoprim and ceftazidime) (60%) respectively. In *pseudomonas aeruginosa*, intrinsic antibiotic resistance is mediated by a decrease of outer membrane permeability, the expression of MDR, XDR and PDR efflux pumps, as well as the synthesis of antimicrobial inactivating enzymes (Hall *et al.*, 2018). In our study, it was observed that the percentages (MDR) were (70%), XDR were (15%) and PDR were (15%), as shown in the figure (3.9). This increase in percentage leads to multiple drug resistance of isolates to antimicrobials because of the province the outer membrane's permeability barrier antibiotics out of the bacterial cells

3.3. Screening and confirmation of ESBLs' production for *K. pneumoniae*

Presumptive ESBLs-producing *K. pneumoniae* were detected in 19 clinical specimens , were initially screened for ESBLs and result 18(94.7%). Of these, 13(68.4%) isolates were determined as ESBLs-producers following confirmatory testing to be ESBLs producers by CLSI complex disk detection (CLSI-CDD) method (modified double-disc synergy test). Resistance of *K. pneumoniae* to cephalosporins (third generation) and monobactams were as the following: cefotaxime: 94.7%, ceftazidime 94.7%, ceftriaxone 94.7%, and aztreonam: 94.7%

3.4. Screening and confirmation of ESBLs' production for *P. aeruginosa*

The clinical isolates 20 of *P. aeruginosa* for ESBL production , were initially screened for ESBLs and result 20(100%) and the confirmatory assay result was 12 (60%) by (modified double-disc synergy test). Resistance of *P. aeruginosa* to third generation cephalosporins and monobactams were as the following: cefotaxime: 90%, ceftazidime: 95%, ceftriaxone: 90%, and aztreonam: 95%.

3.5. Screening and confirmation of ESBLs' production for *E. coli*

Presumptive ESBL-producing *E. Coli* were detected in (17) clinical specimens, were initially screened for ESBLs and result 17(100%) . Of this, 10(58.8%) isolate was determined as ESBLs-producer, following confirmatory testing to be ESBLs producer by (modified double-disc synergy test). Resistance of *E. Coli* to cephalosporins (third generation) and monobactams were as the following: cefotaxime 100%, ceftazidime 100%, ceftriaxone 100%, and aztreonam 100%.

3.6. Screening and confirmation of ESBLs' production for *Proteus mirabilis*

The five *proteus mirabilis* clinical isolates were investigated phenotypically (screen and confirmatory tests) for ESBL production, were initially screened for ESBLs and result 5(100%) The result of the confirmatory examination was 2 (40%). Resistance of *proteus mirabilis* to third generation cephalosporins and monobactams were as the following: cefotaxime: 80%, ceftazidime: 40%, ceftriaxone: 100%, and aztreonam: 40%.

3.7. Screening and confirmation of ESBLs' production for *Acinetobacter baumannii*

the clinical isolates 2 of *Acinetobacter baumannii* were investigated phenotypically (screen and confirmatory tests) for ESBLs production , were initially screened for ESBLs and result was 2(100%)and the confirmatory assay result was (2 100%) . Resistance of *Acinetobacter baumannii* to third generation cephalosporins and monobactams were as the following: cefotaxime: 100%, ceftazidime: 100%, ceftriaxone: 100%, and aztreonam: 100%.

3.8. Molecular detecting Antibiotic Resistance Genes in gram negative bacteria

The results observed that all the isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, *proteus mirabilis*, *Burkholderia cepacia* and *Klebsiella oxytoca*) were negative for the presence of bla_{CTX-M1}, bla_{CTX-M2}, and bla_{CTX-M9} genes. Molecular detection of CTX -M ESBLs for isolate *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed that 1 (8.3%) of the isolate was positive for at least one CTX-M ESBLs gene from 12(60%) , the frequency of CTX-M ESBLs gene presence among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was as follows: bla_{CTX-M1}, 1(8.3%); bla_{CTX-M2}, 1(8.3%); bla_{CTX-M9} 0(0%) ,there was a significant association between the presence of ESBL genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and site of infection ,our study consistent with this study with in Jimma, Ethiopia [33,34] containing this bla_{CTX-M2} in the (3%); (8.2%) respectively. The results was consistent with [35] demonstrated the frequencies of this gene bla_{CTX-M1} (10%) in Erbil.

Detection of CTX -M ESBLs for isolate *Acinetobacter baumannii* 1(50%) of the isolate was positive for at least one CTX-M ESBLs gene, the frequency of CTX-M ESBLs gene from 2(100%) presence among *Acinetobacter baumannii* was as

follows: bla_{CTX-M1}, 0(0%); bla_{CTX-M2}, 1(50%); bla_{CTX-M9} 0(0%) There was a significant association between the presences of ESBL genes .Our study is similar to these studies in in Saudi Arabia [36] carry this gene bla_{CTX-M2} (81%) and another study by [37] carry this gene bla_{CTX-M2} (43%).The agarose gel of PCR products was shown in Figure (3), (4).

Figure 3 Gel electrophoresis of amplified CTXM genes from gram negative bacteria using conventional PCR. Agarose 1.8 %, 100 V/cm for 35 min, visualized on a UV transilluminator. Lane (M): 2000 bp DNA ladder. Lane (1-12) *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolate at product size. CTXM2 404 bp.

Figure 4 Gel electrophoresis of amplified CTXM genes from gram negative bacteria using conventional PCR. Agarose 1.8 %, 100 V/cm for 35 min, visualized on a UV transilluminator. Lane (M): 2000 bp DNA ladder. Lane (1-12): *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolate at product size. CTXM 688 1bp

Beta-lactam antibiotics are being used less and less due to their extensive usage, which has led to a rise in the global dissemination of ESBL enzymes. Therefore, the most effective way to preserve the effectiveness of beta-lactam antibiotics is to fully identify ESBL through trials and restrict the consumption of beta-lactam antibiotics [38].

3.9. TEM, SHA, OXA ESBLs

The results were of bla_{SHV} 3(23%) from isolates *Klebsiella pneumoniae* .Our study is consistent with these studies [39,40] in US hospitals ,these studies have this gene bla_{SHV} (23.5%); (26%) respectively . Compatible with in Wasit [16] this have the gene bla_{SHV} (50%). The result of bla_{SHV} 4(33%) for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ,this result of our study is in agreement with these studies in a Nigerian Teaching Hospital [41,42] that contained this gene in these studies (51%) ; (43%) respectively. The result bla_{SHV} of our study was 2(100%) in *Acinetobacter baumannii*,these results of our study are similar to the results of these studies in Mashhad, Iran [43,44] who carry this gene bla_{SHV} (100%) ; (99%) respectively.

As for the results of bla_{SHV} 1(10%) for one *E. coli* , the results of our study are similar to those of these studies [43,45] in China’s Sichuan-Chongqing Circle. who carry this gene bla_{SHV} (12%) ; (18%) respectively , and agree with this in Wasit

[46] whose result is 13(29%). With regard to the results *bla_{SHV}* 1(50%) for *proteus mirabilis*. Our results are similar to those of these studies in Japan [47,48] in Poland who carry this gene *bla_{SHV}* (50%) ; (58%) respectively.

The results of the gene *bla_{OXA}* 1(10%) were for *E. coli*, our study of this gene is consistent with the results of these studies [49,50] in Germany that contain this gene *bla_{OXA}* (7%) ; (14.9%) respectively. Correspond to the study in Wasit [14] whose result is (17.8%).As for the result *bla_{OXA}* 1(100%), it was for *Burkholderia cepacia* . Our study is similar to the results of these studies [51,52] in the United States who carry this gene *bla_{OXA}* (93%) ; (100%) respectively .As shown figure (5) .However, TEM gene any positive results in all isolation bacteria in this study did not find.

Figure 5 Gel electrophoresis of amplified ESBL genes using conventional PCR. Agarose 1.5 %, 100 V/cm for 40 min, stained with ethidium bromide dye and visualized on a UV transilluminator. Lane (M): 2000 bp DNA ladder. Lane (1-12): some *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *E.coli*, *proteus mirabilis*, *Burkholderia cepacia* isolate at gene product size. SHV 713 bp and OXA-1-like 564bp

4. Conclusion

According to the findings of current study in ICU, The high frequency of specimens collection from intensive care unit patients were isolated from sputum and the gram-negative bacteria were the most common than the positive bacteria. Results of antibiotic susceptibility test revealed that the most active compound against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were Amikacin. Phenotypically and genotypically of ESBLs for *klebsiella pneumoniae* showed no isolate had ESBLs producers CTX-M-type ESBL. The most prevalence of *bla_{SHV}* and no isolate have *bla_{TEM}* and *bla_{OXA-1}* genes, Phenotype and genotype of *pseudomonas aeruginosa* ESBL producers were carrying CTX-M2 and CTX-M1 in their isolates, also prevalence of *bla_{SHV}*. Amp^{CR}- lactamase comprised (*bla_{EBC}*), Phenotype and genotype of ESBLs for *E.Coli* showed no isolate had ESBLs producers CTX-M-type ESBL. Also carries *bla_{SHV}*, *bla_{OXA-1}* and no isolate have *bla_{TEM}* gene.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors like to thank the Alzahraa and Alkarama hospitals for their cooperation

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Çelik, R. and Özel, F. (2020) Comparison of the Rates of Nosocomial Infections in Intensive Care Units. *Kastamonu Health Academic*, 5(2), pp., 159–169.
- [2] Custovic, A., Smajlovic, J., Hadzic, S., Ahmetagic, S., et al. (2014) Epidemiological Surveillance of Bacterial Nosocomial Infections in the Surgical Intensive Care Unit. *Materia socio-medica*, The Academy of Medical Sciences of Bosnia and Herzegovina, 26(1), p., 7.
- [3] Rao, J., Garfinkel, C.I., White, I.P. and Schwartz, C. (2020) The Southern Hemisphere Minor Sudden Stratospheric Warming in September 2019 and Its Predictions in S2S Models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, Wiley Online Library, 125(14), p., e2020JD032723.
- [4] Barsanti, M.C. and Woeltje, K.F. (2009) Infection Prevention in the Intensive Care Unit. *Infectious disease clinics of north America*, Elsevier, 23(3), pp., 703–725.
- [5] Ayobami, O., Willrich, N., Harder, T., Okeke, I.N., et al. (2019) The Incidence and Prevalence of Hospital-Acquired (Carbapenem-Resistant) *Acinetobacter Baumannii* in Europe, Eastern Mediterranean and Africa: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Emerging microbes & infections*, Taylor & Francis, 8(1), pp., 1747–1759.
- [6] Aly, N.Y.A., Al-Mousa, H.H. and el Sayed, M. (2008) Nosocomial Infections in a Medical-Surgical Intensive Care Unit. *Medical Principles and Practice*, Karger Publishers, 17(5), pp., 373–377.
- [7] Qiulian, C., Zhijun, Z. and Yanliang, G. (2021) The Effect of Multidrug-Resistant Infections in Cancer Hospital Intensive Care Unit. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Development*, 35(3).
- [8] Chaudhry, D. and Prajapat, B. (2017) Intensive Care Unit Bugs in India: How Do They Differ from the Western World?. *The Journal of Association of Chest Physicians*, Medknow Publications, 5(1), p., 10.
- [9] Ugwu, M.C., Shariff, M., Nnajide, C.M., Beri, K., et al. (2020) Phenotypic and Molecular Characterization of β -Lactamases among Enterobacterial Uropathogens in Southeastern Nigeria. *Canadian Journal of Infectious Diseases and Medical Microbiology*, Hindawi, 2020.
- [10] Sambrook, J. and Russell, W.D. (2001) *Molecular Cloning: A Laboratory Manual*. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, NY, (1999).
- [11] SAS Institute. (2004) *SAS/STAT 9.1 User's Guide*. Volume 1-7. SAS Institute.
- [12] Abdul-hussein, Z.K., Raheema, R.H. and Inssaf, A.I. (2018) Molecular Diagnosis of Diarrheagenic *E. Coli* Infections among the Pediatric Patients in Wasit Province, Iraq. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*, Oriental Scientific Publishing Company, 12(4), pp., 2229–2241.
- [13] Dahwash, S.M., Raheema, R.H., Albahadili, M.A. and Maslat, A.H. (2021) Distribution of Phylogenetics and Virulence Genes of Uropathogenic *Escherichia Coli* among Urinary Tract Infection in Pregnant Women. *Biochem. Cell. Arch*, 21(1), pp., 449–456.
- [14] Nasser, A., Mosadegh, M., Azimi, T. and Shariati, A. (2022) Molecular Mechanisms of Shigella Effector Proteins: A Common Pathogen among Diarrheic Pediatric Population. *Molecular and Cellular Pediatrics*, SpringerOpen, 9(1), pp., 1–21.
- [15] Raheema, R.H. and Mahood, S. (2018) The Effect of Partial Purified Plantaricin against Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) Induced by *Escherichia Coli* and *Proteus Mirabilis* in Experimental Rat Model. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 623–630, pp., 623–630. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324416223>
- [16] Jassim, A.T., Raheema, R.H. and Melek, H.K. (2022) Characterization of Multidrug Resistant Bacteria Isolated from Patients with Diabetic Foot Ulcers in Wasit Province. *Biochem. Cell. Arch*, 22(1), pp., 000–000. <https://connectjournals.com/03896.2022.22.000>
- [17] Lin, M.-F. (2014) Antimicrobial Resistance in *Acinetobacter Baumannii* : From Bench to Bedside. *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, 2(12), p., 787.
- [18] Albadri, A.T.J. (2021) Characterization and Molecular Study to Detect Multidrug Resistance Bacteria Isolated from Patients with Diabetic Foot Ulcers in Wasit Province .
- [19] Raheema, R.H. and Alsaïdi, M.A. (2016) Protective Effect of Chamomile Recutita Flowers Extract against Urinary Tract Infection Induced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Experimental Mice Models. *J. Health, Medicine and Nursing*, 22, pp., 75–84.

- [20] Al-Saeedi, R.H.A. and Raheema, R.H. (2019) Molecular Diagnosis of Some Virulence Genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Clinical Isolates in Wasit Province. *Indian Journal of Public Health*, 10(04).
- [21] Raheema, R.H. (2016) Effect of Pomegranate Peel Extract on Some Biochemical and Histopathological Parameters in Experimental Induced Mice with *Staphylococcus Aureus*. *Journal of Animal Health and Production*, 4(2), pp., 42–49.
- [22] Raheema, R.H. and Abed, K.A. (2019) Molecular Identification of Virulence Genes of *Staphylococcus Aureus* Isolated from Different Clinical Isolates. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 10(2).
- [23] Raheema, R.H., Melek, H.K. and Atheer, T.J. (2021) Characterization and Molecular Study to Detect Multidrug Resistance Bacteria Isolated from Patients with Diabetic Foot Ulcers in Wasit Province. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 3(2), pp., 201–208.
- [24] Raheema, R.H. (2020) Rapid Methods for Detection of Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* in Wasit Province, Iraq. *Plant Archives*, 20(2), pp., 6131–6134.
- [25] Lorenzoni, V.V., Rubert, F. da C., Rampelotto, R.F. and Hörner, R. (2018) Increased Antimicrobial Resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from a University Hospital in Rio Grande Do Sul, Brazil. *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical*, 51(5), pp., 676–679.
- [26] Ayatollahi, J., Sharifyazdi, M., Fadakarfarid, R. and Shahcheraghi, S.H. (2020) Antibiotic Resistance Pattern of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in Obtained Samples from Ziaee Hospital of Ardakan, Yazd, Iran during 2016 to 2017. *Iberoamerican Journal of Medicine*, Emergency Department of Hospital San Pedro (Logroño, Spain) and the ..., 2(2), pp., 32–36.
- [27] Khandelwal, V. and Sharma, S. (2019) Fatal MDR *Klebsiella* in ICU—How Was It Dealt With?. *Indian Journal of Critical Care Medicine: Peer-reviewed, Official Publication of Indian Society of Critical Care Medicine*, Indian Society of Critical Care Medicine, 23(9), p., 411.
- [28] Mirzaie, A. and Ranjbar, R. (2021) Antibiotic Resistance, Virulence-Associated Genes Analysis and Molecular Typing of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Strains Recovered from Clinical Samples. *AMB Express*, 11(1), p., 122.
- [29] Guragain, N., Pradhan, A., Dhungel, B., Banjara, M.R., et al. (2019) Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamase Producing Gram Negative Bacterial Isolates from Urine of Patients Visiting Everest Hospital, Kathmandu, Nepal. *Tribhuvan University Journal of Microbiology*, 6, pp., 26–31.
- [30] Magiorakos, A.-P., Srinivasan, A., Carey, R.B., Carmeli, Y., et al. (2012) Multidrug-Resistant, Extensively Drug-Resistant and Pandrug-Resistant Bacteria: An International Expert Proposal for Interim Standard Definitions for Acquired Resistance. *Clinical microbiology and infection*, Elsevier, 18(3), pp., 268–281.
- [31] Ali, F., Kamal, S., Shakeela, Q. and Ahmed, S. (2021) Extended-Spectrum and Metallo-Beta Lactamase Enzymes Mediated Resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Clinically Isolated Specimens. *Kuwait Journal of Science*, 48(2).
- [32] Idan, A.K. (2021) Molecular Detection of Some Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Clinical and Hospital Environment. MSc., College of Science Wasit University.
- [33] Kumar, M.R.R., Arunagirinathan, N. and AA, M.A. (2020) Molecular Detection of *CTX-M* Gene in Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases Producing Multidrug-Resistant Gram-Negative Bacterial Isolates. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, , pp., 861–872.
- [34] Majeed Issa, O., Abdul-Elah Bakir, W. and Ayad Abbas, M. (2022) Laboratory Diagnosis of Urinary Tract Infections in Patients with Resistance Genes towards Antibiotics. *Revis Bionatura* 2022; 7 (2) 46.
- [35] Jarjees, K.K., Jarjees, R.K. and Qader, G.M. (2021) Detection of *BlaCTX-M* Genes among Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase Producing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolated from Clinical Specimens in Erbil. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, OMICS International, , pp., 275–282.
- [36] Alyamani, E.J., Khiyami, M.A., Booq, R.Y., Alnafjan, B.M., et al. (2015) Molecular Characterization of Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamases (ESBLs) Produced by Clinical Isolates of *Acinetobacter Baumannii* in Saudi Arabia. *Annals of Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobials*, 14(1), p., 38.
- [37] Saral, A. (2021) Investigation of class 1 integrons with antibiotic resistance genes in multidrug-resistant *acinetobacter baumannii* strains and determination of plant extract effects on multidrug-resistant isolates. *farmacia*, 69(5), pp., 914–918. <https://doi.org/10.31925/farmacia.2021.5.13>

- [38] Saeidi, S., Nezhad, N.M., Javadian, F. and Anbari, M. (2019) Isolation of *CTX-M1*, *CTX-M2*, *CTX-M3* Genes Producing Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase in Clinical Samples of *Salmonella* Typhimurium. *International Journal of Infection*, Briefland, 6(1).
- [39] Castanheira, M., Doyle, T.B., Mendes, R.E. and Sader, H.S. (2019) Comparative Activities of Ceftazidime-Avibactam and Ceftolozane-Tazobactam against Enterobacteriaceae Isolates Producing Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamases from US Hospitals. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*, Am Soc Microbiol, 63(7), pp., e00160-19.
- [40] Ejaz, H., Younas, S., Abosalif, K.O.A., Junaid, K., et al. (2021) Molecular Analysis of *Bla* SHV, *Bla* TEM, and *Bla* *CTX-M* in Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase Producing Enterobacteriaceae Recovered from Fecal Specimens of Animals. *PLoS One*, Public Library of Science San Francisco, CA USA, 16(1), p., e0245126.
- [41] Rezai, M.S., Ahangarkani, F., Rafiei, A., Hajalibeig, A., et al. (2018) Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamases Producing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolated from Patients with Ventilator Associated Nosocomial Infection. *Archives of Clinical Infectious Diseases*, Briefland, 13(4).
- [42] Adekanmbi, A.O., Akinlabi, O.C., Usidamen, S., Olaposi, A.V., et al. (2022) High Burden of ESBL-Producing *Klebsiella* Spp., *Proteus Mirabilis*, *Enterobacter Cloacae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Diagnosed Cases of Urinary Tract Infection in a Nigerian Teaching Hospital. *Acta Microbiologica et Immunologica Hungarica*, Akadémiai Kiadó Budapest, 69(2), pp., 127–134.
- [43] Mlynarcik, P., Chudobova, H., Zdarska, V. and Kolar, M. (2021) In Silico Analysis of Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamases in Bacteria. *Antibiotics*, MDPI, 10(7), p., 812.
- [44] Alshami, H.G.A., Shaye, M.A., Bahreini, M. and Sharifmoghadam, M.R. (2022) Prevalence of Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase Genes and Antibiotic Resistance Pattern in Clinical Isolates of *Acinetobacter baumannii* from Patients Hospitalized in Mashhad, Iran. *Jundishapur Journal of Microbiology*, Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, 15(3), pp., 1–7.
- [45] Zhang, J., Hoedt, E.C., Liu, Q., Berendsen, E., et al. (2021) Elucidation of *Proteus Mirabilis* as a Key Bacterium in Crohn's Disease Inflammation. *Gastroenterology*, Elsevier, 160(1), pp., 317–330.
- [46] Nasser, D.D., Raheema, H.R. and Ahmed, I.A. (2022) Phylogenetic and Molecular Characterization of β -Lactamases among Uropathogenic *Escherichia Coli* from Pediatric Patients in Wasit Province. *Biochem. Cell. Arch.*, 22(1), pp., 000–000.
- [47] Chong, Y., Shimoda, S., Yakushiji, H., Ito, Y., et al. (2013) Community Spread of Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase-Producing *Escherichia Coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Proteus Mirabilis*: A Long-Term Study in Japan. *Journal of medical microbiology*, Microbiology Society, 62(7), pp., 1038–1043.
- [48] Ojdana, D., Sacha, P., Wiczorek, P., Czaban, S., et al. (2014) The Occurrence of *Bla**CTX-M*, *Bla*SHV, and *Bla*TEM Genes in Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase-Positive Strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia Coli*, and *Proteus Mirabilis* in Poland. *International Journal of Antibiotics*, Hindawi, 2014.
- [49] Pulss, S., Stolle, I., Stamm, I., Leidner, U., et al. (2018) Multispecies and Clonal Dissemination of OXA-48 Carbapenemase in Enterobacteriaceae from Companion Animals in Germany, 2009—2016. *Frontiers in microbiology*, Frontiers Media SA, 9, p., 1265.
- [50] Emeraud, C., Biez, L., Girlich, D., Jousset, A.B., et al. (2020) Screening of OXA-244 Producers, a Difficult-to-Detect and Emerging OXA-48 Variant?. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, Oxford University Press, 75(8), pp., 2120–2123.
- [51] Saaid Tuwajj, N.S., Aziz, Z.S. and Al-ghazaly, N.F. (2020) Investigation of Genes Associated with Producing Beta-Lactamase among *Burkholderia Cepacia* Isolates.. *EurAsian Journal of BioSciences*, 14(1).
- [52] Becka, S.A., Zeiser, E.T., LiPuma, J.J. and Papp-Wallace, K.M. (2022) The Class A β -Lactamase Produced by *Burkholderia* Species Compromises the Potency of Tebipenem against a Panel of Isolates from the United States. *Antibiotics*, MDPI, 11(5), p., 674